

PROSPECTS FOR REDUCING POVERTY IN UZBEKISTAN AND IMPROVING THE WELL-BEING OF THE POPULATION

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Anotation: The thesis provides proposals and recommendations for poverty, preventing the problem of poverty, maintaining employment, promoting their aspirations for entrepreneurship, conducting scientific research in order to realize economic reforms, and making solutions to drastically reduce poverty.

Keywords: poverty, poverty, population, prosperity, political reforms

In recent years, Uzbekistan has made significant progress in reducing poverty and improving the well-being of the population. A number of factors contribute to the positive prospects of further reducing poverty and increasing well-being in the country. Such an approach is not only an economic policy, but also a way to self-sustain, create new jobs and seek to improve the country's industrial potential:

1. Economic reforms: Economic reforms, including the abolition of liberation and regulation, are being implemented in the country that attracted foreign investment and stimulated growth. This led to an increase in employment and income levels, which led to lower poverty levels;
2. It is important to focus on agriculture and diversification: Agriculture is an important network that provides employment for a large part of the population in the country. By investing in modern agricultural machinery, irrigation infrastructure and promoting diversification, the government aims to increase agricultural productivity and increase the income of rural residents.
3. Social development programs: The government of Uzbekistan has implemented various social development programs to support people in need of social security, such as targeted money transfers, micro-financial initiatives and vocational training. These programs are aimed at expanding the capabilities of low-income layers, increasing their employability and improving their access to basic services such as education and health care
4. Education and training: Uzbekistan has given priority to educational and advanced training programs to equip its population with the necessary tools to have good job opportunities. Focusing on improving the quality of education,

promoting vocational education, innovation and entrepreneurship, the government aims to reduce poverty and increase wellbeing in the long term.

5. Tourist potential: The rich cultural heritage and historical landmarks of Uzbekistan received international recognition in the years to come, which led to a significant increase in tourism. Further development of the tourism industry will lead to job creation and economic growth, poverty reduction and increased well-being.

While the prospects for reducing poverty and increasing well-being are promising in the country, there are still problems. These problems include addressing regional differences, ensuring inclusive growth, developing good governance and addressing social inequalities. Constant efforts, political reforms and targeted measures will be an important milestone in addressing these problems, sustainable poverty reduction and improving the well-being of the population.

References:

1. Nurmuxamedova B. Davlat byudjeti. O'quv qo'llanma. – T.: Iqtisod- Moliya, 2018. – 575 b.
2. Ляшок В., Татьяна М, Лопатина М. Влияние новых технологий на рынок труда: прошлые уроки и новые вызовы.// Экономическая политика. 2020. Т. 15. № 4. - С. 6,
3. 1999. -Dziobek C., Gutierrez Mangas and P. Kufa (2011). Measuring Fiscal Decentralization – Exploring the IMF's Databases. International Monetary Fund Working Paper 11/126, Washington, DC.
4. Kobulov K. et al. Modeling the processes of forming a strategy for the revenue potential of local budgets // Journal of Advanced Research in Dynamical and Control Systems. – 2020. – Т. 12. – No. 6. – С. 1210-1216.
5. www.gov.uz (O'zbekiston Respublikasi Hukumat portali)
6. www.president.uz (O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining rasmiy veb-sayti)
7. www.stat.uz (O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti huzuridagi Statistika agentligining rasmiy veb-sayti)
8. www.tfi.uz (Toshkent moliya institutining rasmiy veb-sayti)

